

TOOL/PLATFORM FOR PARTICIPATIVE CULTURE IN POST-PANDEMIC ECONOMY CASE STUDY

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Abstract

Purpose – *The paper presents a case study of an innovative digital platform that contributes to the consolidation of participative organizational culture and bonding between employees in the challenging post - pandemic reality.*

Methodology/approach – *For this case study, there first was studied the application and the documentation we were given access to. Afterwards we conducted interviews with the core development team and users of Digital Democracy platform and the last stage was to conduct workshops to evaluate the expected impact.*

Findings – *Although the presented tool was initially destined for other purpose, we find it's valuable impact on cultures of challenged organizations in post-pandemic time.*

Research limitations/implications – *The case study concludes the information's received by the development team of the Digital Democracy platform and its beneficiaries.*

Practical implications – *Possible implementation of staff, members, colleagues engaging platforms and further development possibilities of the platform.*

Originality/value – *Although the instrument was initially designed to increase the civic spirit in communities, it proves itself very useful to combat personnel fluctuation in organizations. For a period, it's "side-effects" have proven to have a more valuable immediate impact.*

Key words: *Social dialogue, Participative organizational culture, Community, Digital platform, digital democracy*

Introduction

How does post-pandemic reality change organizations around the world? What are the new challenges for employers in a mixture of hybrid work conditions? How do Human Resources Managers react to this? What are the significant factors that keep people together in organizations? What role plays the participative culture and how does it fit with hierarchy discipline? What changed after the covid lockdowns? These are some basic questions witch answers could bring some clarity in these unstable times.

In our opinion, the new reality described by remote job opportunities and social distancing is shaping the organizational performance in many fields. Except the few segments, where people are geographic or work specific restricted to the workplace, remote work opens a completely new opportunities and also challenges for both managers and employees.

At the same time, after spending so much time in "social-distancing" people start to be more and more selective with where and for what they decide to spend their time and involvement. Massive resignation phenomena appear all over the world. One of the key questions for employers nowadays should be the reiteration of mission-vision and the strengths of their own organizational culture! In democratic countries, it is no surprise that employees are more productive, better performing and have a higher involvement in participative organizational cultures. Together with the "sense of belonging" and

identification with the organizational values, participative culture is highly contributing to high performers retention.

One of the instruments that actively contribute to participative organizational culture in organizations is Digital Democracy platform. This digital platform was designed and first developed by a core team from Cluj-Napoca, Romania. This case-study presents the benefits this innovative tool can bring into organizations.

About the online platform Digital Democracy

How did the platform Digital Democracy start? Alexandru Boc, founder of Digital Democracy and his team explained the founding principles and the idea behind the platform:

Started in 2016 with the design of the concept. Initially the plan was to create an application dedicated to urban local Romanian communities, but later, the concept was extended for larger communities like counties or even countries.

The need: First, there was an analysis regarding how democracy will evolve, and the analysis of the status-quo and the fields where democracy is not yet using the best technology -which in our opinion is the digital one. In order to help engage and involve as many actors as possible like NGO's, companies, citizens, and public institutions, there was a need of a digital application which can provide real time transparency and efficiency.

Motivation for starting the project was the desire for a better world! The natural evolution of democracy will make us use of digital tools. The team designed a special concept for communities with five major fields of interest: Education, Health, Economy, Public Administration and Entertainment.

Regarding the mission of Digital Democracy, it is designed to significantly grow the level of democratic exercise world-wide starting down top starting with the local communities. Our role is to build the best mobile app to help and facilitate the engagement of people and authorities and boost the level of appreciation regarding the democratic values.

The target of the platform is to bring together for initiatives, events and polls, in our opinion, four main actors in a democratic society: Citizens, Companies, NGO's and Public Institutions.

The solution of a digital platform came because the digitalization is for now, the most accessible technological solution and democracy is, in our opinion the best organizational form.

The development level of democracy will evolve, but it can also devolve. This is why it is important for us all to get involved in the communities we live in. The easiest and most accessible way to do so, is by using the designated applications from used on various devices, like smartphones.

Key aspects regarding the Digital Democracy tool

The developers of Digital Democracy tool present that their vision is to live in a society where the societal challenges and problems are solved with the direct and real-time input of the citizens and stakeholders involved. Also, the mission is to increase the level of democracy around the world, from local communities to global ones by creating the best digital tool for increasing democracy awareness and involvement.

The main role of the Digital Democracy platform is to solve the problem of difficult interconnectivity between social stakeholders: Government, Companies, NGO's and Citizens, which actually has in their opinion four main causes: low civic participation, lack of digitalization, excessive bureaucracy and lack of meaningful data. Data without an algorithm and transformed in added value, is just trash.

The platform was first designed as an MVP product, prepared for a seed funding. Currently it is launched in a beta version for over 600 beta users. The interest of usage, after come marketing investment raised to over 68k interested users.

According to the data, we mention some key figures. The first indicator, according to the Public Opinion Monitor of the European Parliament, in 2020, 52% of EU citizens don't interact with NGOs. As shown in

Figure 1. Engagement level with NGO in the European Union, in countries that joined the Union later, the rate of engagement with NGO's is far lower.

The bureaucracy is another important aspect. There is around 5 billion € potential cost reduction in EU with digital bureaucracy and also taking into consideration that in 2019 there was a 50.6% turnout in EU elections.

Figure 1. Engagement level with NGO in EU (Source: Public Opinion Monitor of the European Parliament)

The Digital Democracy team considers bringing a solution consisting in a “unique e-democracy platform connecting four stakeholder groups with the purpose of initiating discussions and work towards solving challenges. By connecting on five focus areas (Education, Health, Economy, Entertainment and Public administration) the four actors (Citizens, NGO's, Companies and Public Institutions) through their innovative mobile app.

From initial goal to valuable “side-effects”

The main reason why we present this specifically this case study is because of it's valuable side-effects.

Initially, the Digital Democracy application was developed in order to increase interorganizational collaboration, civic engagement, to strengthen communities, to bring main social actors together and help them interact on main categories of interests.

Now, in the post-pandemic reality, organizations have to consolidate their internal culture in order to face the great resignation trend, stability and sense of belonging are key aspects which influence the personnel retention. Already, many employers define their organizational structure as a community and the idea of creating participative organizational culture at least at some levels of rather less important business matters becomes more and more attractive to human resource directors and top management.

In these times, the Digital Democracy application can prove very useful for organizations. The possibility to set the access to their own organization, as shown the micro-organizational community brings great value for each organization. Members or employees can interact, collaborate, participate in certain topics of interest. Of course, the topics are highly adapted to the companies or organization needs.

Thus, a new filed of application for this platform, the stability of personal structure, reveals new beneficiaries for the original Digital Democracy application: organizations. The larger the structure, the more impact, such an app can bring into the organization. Practically having a employer engaging

platform where each employee manages its profile, work, career, results and performance indicators in a digital passport in collaboration with the employer.

Discussion and conclusions

In the post-pandemic reality, bringing together and retain top performers is a major challenge. The organizational shift from “employers” to “community members” is already happening and employees appreciate the “sense of belonging”, while a participative organizational culture, where “their opinion matters” is crucial to keep motivated high performers.

As digital technology creates easy access to information and facilitates interaction, digital platforms and applications are highly appreciated and become indispensable tools in management of HR and organizational culture. Digital Democracy, the application presented in this paper is one example. Although the application was designed before the pandemics for its initial goal, it proves herself very useful in post-pandemic times specially to strengthen internal collaboration and the participative organizational culture.

Trends appear and organizations and communities must decide in which way they should focus on and spent resources. One way is to encourage interorganizational collaboration, which before the Covid-19 pandemic was rather the mainstream. The other option is rather to focus on the internal community, which now, in post-pandemic times is a must to counter the great resignation phenomenon. Since digitalization is already very accessible and social media platforms already impact the mindset and interests of the employees or community members. The level of courteousness between key players on allocating resources rather to interorganizational collaboration versus internal collaboration remains a further research topic as well as the effort and investment that employers make to strengthen the internal communities.

Notes

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Employers' Organization for Research and Digitization considers that the development of innovative products in Romania should be encouraged, also through the documentation and presentation of case studies. The presentation of this case study does not have any commercial interests.

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